

Quality Assessment of Chest Radiographs

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Abstract. The COVID-19 pandemic has created the need to analyse a huge number of chest radiographs. However, not all radiographs are acquired with the same parameters or conditions and many radiographs that are available present various levels of quality. One way to assess the quality of a radiograph is to measure the contrast. In the particular case of chest x-rays, the contrast of interest is not a general contrast measurement, but rather it is between the darker regions of the lungs and the brighter surrounding regions; the edges of the ribcage and the sternum. Due to the position of the bright and dark regions, a profile projection resembles a letter "W" with three peaks and two valleys. This work describes a simple, yet effective, algorithm to assess the quality of the chest radiographs based on the intensity projections of images. The quality is a derived metric of contrast between peaks and valleys. The algorithm is freely available through GitHub.

1 Introduction

This work describes the assessment of the quality of a chest radiograph based on the contrast X-ray. The algorithm used to assess this quality derives a metric based on the contrast between the intensity of the regions of lungs (which should be dark) and the intensity of the chest and the edge of the ribs (which should be brighter) in order to assess the quality of a Chest Radiograph in a Posterior-Anterior (PA) orientation. This contrast is measured by detecting the median intensity projection over each column of the radiograph.

The projection should roughly resemble the shape of a "W" with three peaks corresponding to the brighter regions and two valleys corresponding to the darker regions (Fig. 1).

In an idealised situation, the three peaks would have the same intensity as well as the two valleys. However, in real radiographs this is not the case. Thus the metric is calculated by measuring the depth of the two valleys separately and selecting *the smallest of both metrics*.

2 Algorithm Description

All the code was developed in Matlab® (The MathworksTM, Natick, MA, USA). The first step is to obtain a projection over the vertical direction. There are several projections that can be used. For this work, the median projection has been selected, but it is also possible to use a mean projection. To avoid noise (which can be due to annotations in the radiograph) a low pass filter to the projection is applied.

2.1 Peak detection

This algorithm detects three peaks using the function *findpeaks*. Neighbouring peaks are not considered as well as peaks with low prominence. Then, any peaks that are close to the edges of the radiograph are discarded. In case there are more than three peaks, the three with highest prominence are selected. If there are only 2 peaks detected, the central peak is located and the missing peak is set at the opposite side of the existing, at the same distance as the existing one to the central peak. Fig. 2 shows the median projection as a red line and the peaks with blue circles. Additionally, maximum and minimum projections are shown in black and magenta solid lines respectively. Other labels and annotations are described below.

2.2 Valley detection

Once the peaks have been detected, valleys are detected, again with *findpeaks* over the same profile line with the intensity inverted. Any valley that is outside the peaks (left or right) is discarded. If there are no valleys detected (imagine a very low contrast radiograph), these are set at the midpoints between peaks and the same is done in case there is only one detected. If there are more than two valleys, then the most prominent ones are selected. Fig. 2 shows the valleys as green stars.

2.3 Metric calculation

The depth between the bottom of each valley and the average intensity of the two neighbouring peaks is calculated. An absolute metric is calculated as the *minimum* of the two intensity differences between corresponding to each valley and the average intensities of the peaks at each side. In a normal case, these two intensities are similar, but if one lung is much brighter than the other, then the intensities are different. An alternative to the minimum is to calculate the average. Fig. 2 shows the metrics of each valleys as a vertical green line from the intensity of the level of the valley to the average between the two peaks. Notice that the valleys do not necessarily locate halfway between the peak locations.

Then, to make this as a relative metric, the intensity of the whole image is analysed with order statistics to determine a lower value (6%) and a higher value (99%). The higher value is closer to the maximum as it is only necessary to discard the maximum values which can be due to labels on a radiograph. However, the lower value should be higher than a 1% to cover for dark pixels which can be background. Fig. 2 shows the high value as a dashed black line with diamond markers and the low value as a dashed magenta line with diamond markers.

Finally, the metric is the ratio of the absolute metric previously calculated divided by the difference between the high and low values of the order statistics. Fig. 2 shows the absolute metric, the denominator as the difference between high and low intensity values and the relative metric above the radiograph.

2.4 Graphical display

The function returns the actual metric (values between 0 and 1) and if requested a graphical display with a figure with 4 subplots: 1) the original radiographs, 2,3) intensity projections over the rows and columns, (maximum intensity projection, - black, minimum intensity projection - magenta, median intensity projection - red) 4) the radiograph with the contrast adjusted to the low and high values.

The intensity projection of each column shows the location of the peaks (blue circles), lines connecting the peaks (dashed blue lines), valleys (green stars), the intensity differences between the level of the valleys and the intermediate points of the peaks (thin vertical green lines), the lower and higher intensity values (magenta and black respectively).

The function is called with two parameters, the image itself, and an optional parameter to plot (1). The only output parameter is the metric.

3 Examples

A few examples are shown below. The images are read from the Covid-Chest-dataset compiled by Joseph Paul Cohen in the GitHub repository "ieee8023" [2]. The examples are displayed in a decreasing level of the quality metric.

3.1 Example 1

The first example is a high contrast image with very well defined peaks and valleys. The image is read directly from the GitHub repository and then the function outputs the result directly with the second input parameter (1).

```
currImage=imread('https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ieee8023/
covid-chestxray-dataset/master/images/covid-19-pneumonia-30-PA.jpg');
quMetric = QualityChestXray(currImage,1);
```

3.2 Example 2

Second example with lower contrast. The peaks and valleys are well defined. As the image is relatively bright, the low intensity level is high (dashed magenta line) and then when the intensity is adjusted (bottom right) the image has higher contrast and can be better visualised. This also increases the relative metric as the denominator is reduced by the smaller difference between the high and low intensity values (244 – 140). See next example.

```
currImage=imread('https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ieee8023/
covid-chestxray-dataset/master/images/pneumocystis-pneumonia-12.png');
quMetric = QualityChestXray(currImage,1);
```

3.3 Example 3

This is another example of medium contrast, and as the image is not as bright as the previous example, even if the valleys seem deeper than the previous case (66 v. 41) the relative metric is smaller.

```
currImage=imread('https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ieee8023/
covid-chestxray-dataset/master/images/covid-19-pneumonia-43-day0.jpeg');
quMetric = QualityChestXray(currImage,1);
```

3.4 Example 4

Fourth example of a lower quality image. The peaks are not that well defined and the metric is lower than previous both in absolute (35) and relative terms (0.25).

```
currImage=imread('https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ieee8023/
covid-chestxray-dataset/master/images/covid-19-pneumonia-41-day-2.jpg');
quMetric = QualityChestXray(currImage,1);
```

3.5 Example 5

Final example of a very low quality radiograph. It is interesting to notice that the peaks and valleys are still reasonable even for the low quality. The high intensity value is biased by the large annotation at the bottom. The 1% calculation can be reconsidered in cases like this one. Still, the metric is very low both in absolute (22) and relative terms (0.09).

```
currImage=imread('https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ieee8023/
covid-chestxray-dataset/master/images/all14238-fig-0002-m-d.jpg');
quMetric = QualityChestXray(currImage,1);
```

4 Conclusions

An algorithm to measure the quality of posterior-anterior radiographs has been described. The algorithm exploits the contrast between lungs and surrounding regions through the detections of peaks and valleys in the median intensity projection over the vertical dimension. One possible application of this algorithm is to rank images them by quality from best to worst. Another application can be to select images above a certain quality threshold and discard those below. This can be particularly useful in deep learning settings where low quality samples can bias the training of architectures.

5 Code

All the code was developed in Matlab® (The MathworksTM, Natick, MA, USA) and is available open-source in GitHub from: <https://github.com/reyesaldasoro/QualityChestXray>

References

1. Häggström, M.: Normal posteroanterior (PA) chest radiograph (X-ray) (2017), [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Normal_posteroanterior_\(PA\)_chest_radiograph_\(X-ray\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Normal_posteroanterior_(PA)_chest_radiograph_(X-ray).jpg), wikimedia Commons
2. Cohen, J.P.: <https://github.com/ieee8023/covid-chestxray-dataset> (Jun 2020), [ieee8023/covid-chestxray-dataset](https://github.com/ieee8023/covid-chestxray-dataset)

Fig. 1. Illustration of the intensity projections and the three bright peaks and two dark valleys, which together form a shape that resembles a letter "W". For each valley, the depth can be measured as the difference of intensity from the bottom of the valley to the average of the two neighbouring peaks. Radiograph credit [1].

Fig. 2. Image with high contrast (Metric = 0.58). The original radiograph is shown in the top left. Projections are shown at the right and bottom and an intensity adjusted radiograph is shown in the bottom right. This example does not change significantly as it has high contrast. For a description of the labels, see section 2.4.

Fig. 3. Medium Contrast (0.40). Notice the difference between the original radiograph and the intensity adjusted one.

Fig. 4. Medium Contrast (0.32)

Fig. 5. Medium Contrast (0.25)

Fig. 6. Medium Contrast (0.09). Notice that despite the low contrast of the image, the "W" shape is still detected.